

STUDY OF ACUTE TOXICITY OF "PHYTOBRONCHIS"**Zayniddinova D.G.****Sultanova R.Kh.****Shiltsova N.V**

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Introduction. Inflammatory processes underlie the development of most diseases, be it pathology of the respiratory tract, gastrointestinal tract, joints or skin. Modern medicine has a wide range of anti-inflammatory drugs, but their prolonged use is often accompanied by side effects and complications. In this regard, there is a growing interest in the use of natural remedies, in particular herbal preparations with anti-inflammatory activity. Medicinal plants contain flavonoids, essential oils, tannins and other biologically active components that have a mild but pronounced anti-inflammatory effect.

Actuality. The use of anti-inflammatory herbal preparations is important for both the prevention and comprehensive treatment of diseases. Natural compositions have a multicomponent effect: they not only reduce inflammation, but also have antioxidant, immunomodulatory and restorative effects. Against the background of growing interest in phytotherapy and the search for safe alternatives to synthetic drugs, the study of the composition and effectiveness of anti-inflammatory herbal preparations is becoming particularly relevant in modern medicine and pharmacology.

The purpose of the study: "To study the acute toxicity (LD_{50}) of the amount of flavonoids with the conditional name "Phytobronchis".

Methods: The acute toxicological safety of the studied fraction was evaluated on healthy white mongrel mice of both sexes weighing 18-20 g, kept in standard vivarium conditions with unlimited access to water and specialized feed." The animals were injected with an aqueous solution in the range of 100.0-16500.0 mg/kg once a day.

The results of the study. When the amount of flavonoids with the conditional name "Phytobronchis" was administered orally to white mice (18-20 g) in doses of 100-9000 mg / kg, no changes in behavior and reactions to stimuli were detected. In the range of 10000-14000 mg/kg, there was a short-term decrease in activity, rapid breathing and weakening of muscle tone, which lasted for 40 minutes. At a dose of 15,000 mg/kg, similar manifestations were observed without fatal outcomes during 14 days of follow-up. LD_{50} was observed at a dose of 15183.4 (14481.0 \pm 15729.6). Based on the data obtained on the average lethal dose, we determined the toxicity class according to the classifier described in the methodological guide for preclinical drug research edited by Stefanov A.V. According to this classifier, the drug belongs to the fifth class of toxicity when administered orally.

Conclusion. The experimental results showed that the amount of Phytobronchis flavonoids has pharmacological activity, is characterized by practically non-toxic.